

World Cafes

Day one kicked off with the [OXIPRO World Cafes](#) for researchers, PhD students, and young professionals passionate about creating a more sustainable world. The chosen themes generated broad and stimulating discussions on green choices, fast fashion, and food waste to understand consumer needs and expectations. In essence, it was agreed that:

- 👉 A major cultural change is needed
- 👉 Biotech can play a role, sometimes small but can be essential
- 👉 Researchers can lead change, be role models and raise awareness

Info Day

Day two - [Info Day](#) - brought the four projects together to share insights through engaging panel discussions and presentations. The overarching messages are that:

- ➔ Stakeholder engagement is key to meeting societal needs and expectations
- ➔ Sustainability is about choosing low footprints, but needs enablers for greener solutions
- ➔ Public-private partnerships broaden participants' capabilities

Spring School

Day three - the [Spring School](#) - offered a unique educational opportunity to gain insights from industry leaders and researchers, with hands-on workshops, networking and chocolate for PhD students and postdocs interested in the enzyme and biotechnology fields.

[Read more](#)

Latest Research Developments

Leitat Develops Innovative Enzyme Screening Platform for Enhanced Efficiency and Reusability

Leitat unveils a new bioreactor that uses less reagent and offers over ten reuse cycles, driving cost-effective, eco-friendly enzyme testing.

[Read more](#)

OXIPRO Unveils Innovative Biocatalytic Process for Sustainable Cotton Bleaching

A breakthrough bioprocess reduces chemical use and energy consumption in cotton bleaching, marking a big win for greener textiles.

[Read more](#)

Revolutionizing Laundry Hygiene: Enzyme-Based Method Promises Eco-Friendly Solutions

OXIPRO advances an enzyme-based laundry sanitization method that could replace chemical disinfectants for a greener future.

[Read more](#)

Computational Platforms: Enhancing Enzyme Discovery with 'Horus'

Learn how OXIPRO's Horus platform leverages computational power to accelerate enzyme discovery and design.

Gecco and RUG Enhance Food Preservation and Personal Care Products

Discover enzyme-based innovations improving food preservation and sustainability in personal care.

[Read more](#)

Our Policy Work

European Cluster Enzymes for Greener Products
Policy Brief | April 2025
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15148731

Integrating Enzyme Technologies into EU Policy Frameworks

Executive Summary
Enzyme technologies are revolutionising industries by providing sustainable, efficient, and non-toxic alternatives to conventional chemical-based processes. These innovations directly align with the European Union's (EU) safety goals under the European Green Deal¹, Circular Economy Action Plan², Safe and Sustainable by Design framework (SSbD)³, and the Clean Industrial Deal⁴. However, regulatory inconsistencies – particularly within chemical classifications – pose significant barriers to the widespread adoption of enzyme-based solutions.

This policy brief draws insights from the FNR-16 projects (EnVitaScope, FutuEnzyme, OXIPRO, and Risdical2) and extensive stakeholder and consumer surveys, highlights the economic and environmental benefits of enzyme technologies, identifies regulatory obstacles, and provides clear policy recommendations to position enzymes as catalysts for Europe's green and digital transition.

At the same time, it emphasises the urgent need to adapt EU regulations to fully harness enzyme technologies as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemicals.

Key Messages
Enzyme technologies are essential enablers of sustainable innovation. They reduce reliance on hazardous chemicals, lower energy and water use, and support the circular economy across sectors like textiles, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and detergents.

Current EU regulations, especially under REACH, create barriers to enzyme adoption. Automatic classification of enzymes as hazardous substances (e.g. respiratory sensitisers) does not reflect their actual use-case safety, limiting innovation and market access.

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks must better integrate sustainability. The SSbD process should consider not only safety but also environmental and socio-economic benefits of enzyme technologies, using balanced and holistic assessment approaches.

Policy support and regulatory streamlining are urgently needed. Fast-track approval pathways, harmonised regulations across member states, and reduced burdens for SMEs will help accelerate the uptake of enzyme-based innovations.

Investing in enzyme technologies will strengthen EU industrial competitiveness. Supporting enzyme innovation in biomanufacturing aligns with the EU Green Deal, Clean Industrial Deal, and Bioeconomy Strategy, positioning the EU as a global leader in sustainable industry.

Enzymes are proteins that act as biological catalysts and help speed up chemical reactions

OXIPRO Policy Brief
March 2025

Progressing the 'Safe and Sustainable by Design' Framework for Greener Enzyme-based Innovations

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Key Messages:

- Prioritization of hazard assessment in SSbD excludes OXIPRO's enzyme-based solutions despite their environmental impact potential creating a major gap in the evaluation of substances that could contribute significantly to European sustainability goals.
- The SSbD assessment of OXIPRO's enzyme-based innovations faced challenges typical of early-stage innovations, where risk and exposure data are scarce or limited, and assessment methods are not yet well-developed.
- Addressing these barriers requires fostering collaboration and SSbD training, refining methods for early-stage assessments, and alignment of policies.

Purpose:
This policy brief presents recommendations derived from the experience in using the SSbD framework in the context of four enzyme-based innovation cases in the Horizon Europe funded OXIPRO project¹, as policy input for future refinement of the framework.

The urgency for transitioning to safer and more sustainable chemical solutions
Chemicals are crucial for societal function and economic performance, yet they contribute to climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss² and threaten human health. A 2024 survey found that 84% of the over 26,000 respondents expressed concern about the effects of harmful chemicals in everyday products on their health³, with an equal proportion also worried about their impact on the environment. This underpins the need for more proactive risk assessment before marketing chemicals.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000607>; <https://www.oxipro.eu/>
² United Nations Environment Programme, International Science Council, Navigating New Horizons: A global foresight report on planetary health and human wellbeing; Nairobi, 2022
³ European Commission, Attitudes of Europeans towards the Environment. Special Eurobarometer 550, 2024

New Joint Policy Brief Urges EU Support and Action to Unlock and Integrate the Power of Enzyme Technologies

OXIPRO and our sister projects call for stronger EU support for enzyme innovations to accelerate Europe's green and digital transition.

[Read more](#)

Progressing the 'Safe and Sustainable by Design' Framework for Greener Enzyme-based Innovations

New policy recommendations from OXIPRO contribute to improving the EU's sustainability framework for chemical innovations.

[Read more](#)

Publications and Articles

FOUNDATIONS AND FRONTIERS IN ENZYMOLOGY

Laccase and Polyphenol Oxidase
Biochemistry and Biotechnological Applications

Edited by Ivanhoe K.H. Leung
Series Editor: Munishwar Nath Gupta

Contents list available at [OXIPRO](#)

Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering
Journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jce

Towards a resource friendly circular cotton processing: From carbohydrate rich wastewaters to hydrogen peroxide using carbohydrate oxidases

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ABSTRACT
One of the main issues in the textile industry is the treatment of wastewater generated from cotton processing. This wastewater contains high concentrations of carbohydrates, which are a source of pollution. In this work, a bioprocess is proposed to convert these carbohydrates into hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) using carbohydrate oxidases (COs). The bioprocess is based on the use of a yeast strain that produces COs. The H₂O₂ produced is used as a bleaching agent in the cotton processing. The bioprocess is sustainable and resource efficient, as it uses renewable resources and produces a valuable by-product. The bioprocess is also environmentally friendly, as it reduces the carbon footprint of the cotton processing. The bioprocess is also economically viable, as it reduces the costs of cotton processing. The bioprocess is also socially responsible, as it creates jobs and improves the quality of life of the community. The bioprocess is also a promising approach to improve the cotton processing.

1. Introduction
Cotton fibres, along with other plant-based fibres, have been used for thousands of years, primarily to produce textiles. The textile industry is one of the most important sectors in the world, and it is also one of the most polluting. The textile industry generates a large amount of wastewater, which contains high concentrations of carbohydrates. These carbohydrates are a source of pollution, and they can be converted into hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) using carbohydrate oxidases (COs). The H₂O₂ produced is used as a bleaching agent in the cotton processing. The bioprocess is sustainable and resource efficient, as it uses renewable resources and produces a valuable by-product. The bioprocess is also environmentally friendly, as it reduces the carbon footprint of the cotton processing. The bioprocess is also economically viable, as it reduces the costs of cotton processing. The bioprocess is also socially responsible, as it creates jobs and improves the quality of life of the community. The bioprocess is also a promising approach to improve the cotton processing.

Enzymes in Detergents: A Game-Changer for Sustainability

A new article from NORCE explains how enzyme solutions are transforming the detergent industry for

Enzymatic Innovation for Sustainable Cotton Processing

Highlighting sustainable cotton processing through enzymatic innovations from OXIPRO in a new paper

a greener future

by our team at UAB.

[Read more](#)

[Read more](#)

OXIPRO Partners Lead the Way in Transforming Laccase Research

OXIPRO researchers publish a book chapter and push the boundaries in understanding and applying laccase enzymes.

[Read more](#)

How Enzymes are Leading the Way to a More Sustainable Future

Unveiling the critical role of enzymes in achieving a greener, more sustainable world in an article published in the Project Repository Journal.

[Read more](#)

Our Recent Activities

OXIPRO Roundtable: Shaping the Future of Sustainable Biotechnology

OXIPRO partners engaged with key stakeholders on the future of sustainable biotech during a dedicated roundtable event held in Brussels. A full report will be available very soon.

[Read more](#)

Bridging Science and Industry: Showcasing Enzymatic Innovations at Biocat4Value

OXIPRO researchers established strong connections between academia and industry at the Biocat4Value Biocatalysis Conference in Düsseldorf, Germany.

[Read more](#)

Showcasing our nutraceutical and sunscreen innovation cases at SSbD Event

Our researchers highlighted sustainable innovation in consumer products using safe-and-sustainable-by-design approaches at key SSbD event in Switzerland.

[Read more](#)

Partner Spotlight - SBSM Science Management

Discover the role of SBSM in leading OXIPRO's Responsible Research and Innovation work package and how they are supporting the environmental sustainability goals of the project.

Find out about the people involved in this dynamic team!

[Read more](#)

What do YOU think?

It's vital for ALL new innovations that researchers and industry find out if they meet the needs of consumers and what end-users' expectations and preferences are. And we are all end-users.

So please **take just TWO minutes of your time** to complete our short survey by following the link below or use the QR code.

The Survey..

https://bit.ly/oxipro_survey_1

The Active Site - The final enzyme cluster newsletter

We are excited to announce the release of the final issue of "The Active Site" newsletter! This edition is packed with exciting updates, ground-breaking research, and insightful articles that highlight the latest advancements in enzyme technology and their transformative impact across various industries.

[Read all issues of Active Site here](#)

Our sister projects are:

- [EnXylaScope](#)
- [FuturEnzyme](#)
- [Radicalz](#)

And finally...

We hope you've found this issue of OXIPRO'S news of interest.

[Check out our news page](#)

[Read back issues of our newsletter and more of our output](#)

And please [register via our website](#) to stay up to date with our developments and events.

We hold stakeholder consultations with representatives from different fields who assist us in filling knowledge gaps and identifying requirements.

If you want to know how we engage those interested in OXIPRO, we've taken a "scientific approach" and [published our guide](#) on how to develop a stakeholder engagement plan.

www.oxipro.eu/contact/

About OXIPRO

OXIPRO is a four-year initiative funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme and brings together a multidisciplinary team of researchers and stakeholders from 15 entities across Europe to focus on the development of novel enzymes for environment-friendly consumer products.

The OXIPRO partners are developing and deploying an efficient oxidoreductase foundry using cutting-edge bioinformatics and biotechnology, and by broadening the range of industrial oxidoreductases for more sustainable processes, this initiative will ultimately contribute to the transition to environment-friendly products, with detergents, textiles, sunscreens, and nutraceuticals.

Through the integration of computational workflows and state-of-the-art biotechnological technologies, OXIPRO will expedite the lab to market journey, while shortcutting downstream implementation and ensuring market uptake. This will be supported by ecosystem intelligence generated throughout the project as well as engagement with research, policy, societal and industrial actors in co-creation and interactions to maximise output and enable faster and systemic innovations.

For more information, contact:

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Communications: [Lesley Tobin](#)

To join the OXIPRO Community and receive project updates, [please register here](#)

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